

TEACHING ENGLISH IN AN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. One of the priority areas of general education is the development of children with special educational needs. A child in this category is a special child, and the requirements of the standard education system do not apply to them.

An important task of modern society is to develop and preserve every child. It is assumed that teachers in their practical activities should show sensitive attention to each child, his abilities and characteristics.

Keywords: child with special educational needs, inclusive education, foreign language, educational abilities.

A special educational need is a mental quality that develops over the course of a person's life, which determines the importance of achieving results in certain types of activities.

An inclusive child is a complex mental education in which volitional, cognitive, motivational, psychophysiological, emotional, and other mental properties are insufficiently formed or absent, the development or extinction of which is due to personal, social, and pedagogical factors.

The family plays a big role in the development of children with disabilities. In the family, the child has all the qualities and prospects of development. Society, schools and professional institutions must do everything possible to ensure that children are able to realize their potential to the extent necessary for them.

Language is also an academic discipline, and at the same time a means of expanding cooperation, achieving mutual understanding, and enriching the culture of the individual. In the methodology of teaching English, the main emphasis is placed on the formation of communicative competence, the development of communication skills based on knowledge of the world.

This method makes it possible to take into account the essence of language as one of the main tools of human activity and thinking, as a means of becoming a person, focuses on the personality of a teenager and allows you to more closely link the educational process with a foreign language culture. First of all, the teacher should interest children in the significance of the subject, enrich their vocabulary, teach them to think logically, engage in creative tasks, awaken their imagination, and do everything possible to develop a child with special educational needs.

The ideal way to work in foreign language classes with special children is to use an individual teacher. The teacher "guides" the student. At the beginning of training, the teacher must find an approach to each child, so that they have their own "piggy bank of knowledge" and a good incentive for further training.

When working with children with special educational needs, the teacher tries to create conditions where students want to listen to a foreign language, speak short phrases and expressions in a foreign language. Students, feeling the attention of the teacher and friends to themselves, are more easily involved in foreign language activities and experience a sense of joy and pleasure from classes.

It is important to help the teenager to believe in himself, to create a sense of success, to overcome the fear of making mistakes. In this case, it is possible to take a proactive approach when a strong student who has mastered the material receives individual tasks that correspond to the complexity of his abilities, and allows him to quickly master the language environment.

‘The use of musical exercises in foreign language lessons allows the teacher to include the reserve capabilities of the child's personality in active cognitive activity, creates prerequisites for friendly collective work in an atmosphere of positive emotions.

A close relationship exists between the development of musical and speech hearing. When using musical texts, the development of auditory attention and control appears, and the operation of the articulatory apparatus improves. Such classes are included in the work in the first 4 months of training, when children's immersion in the language environment, familiarity with sound and speaking plays a more important role, while children are not familiar with the rules of reading and writing.

Goals and objectives that the teacher sets for himself when conducting classes:

1. Use of communicative and theatrical techniques using modern ICT.
2. Conducting individual classes-consultations, extracurricular and project activities on the subject.
3. The principle of dividing students into groups.

From the practice of teaching, you can understand that language projects are necessary. The project is based on a task or problem that requires students to perform research and independent activities outside of school hours and in the classroom. Students take part in tests, quizzes, contests, and Olympiads with great interest.

There are the following main features inherent in children with special educational abilities in the process of learning a foreign language:

Positive ones: Optimistic attitude no matter what; Kindness; Responsiveness; The desire to learn new things

Negative: intolerance, striving for leadership, excessive demands on others, non-acceptance of traditional teaching methods.

The main approaches to working with children with disabilities are:

Low pace of classes and high intensity.

Lowering the difficulty level of tasks.

The main forms and methods of working in English classes are::

1. Role-playing games.
2. Performing creative exercises.
3. Create presentations and projects.
4. Integrated learning (inter-subject communication).
5. Extracurricular activities.

When preparing for a lesson for children who learn the material much faster, the teacher should think through various additional tasks. Additional training of grammatical phenomena, pronouncing active vocabulary and speech situations that were studied in the lesson, allow you to move on to a new topic with full confidence that the child has fully mastered the previous material. Students who have successfully mastered the material are invited to participate in various creative subject competitions.

The methods and techniques of teaching discussed above are aimed at supporting the cognitive interest of students, forming the need and ability of the individual to self-development, creating maximum conditions for the development of the child's potential.

Will the child become a talented person with signs of children's disabilities? This depends on a wide range of reasons and factors. Adults play an important role in this, and the teacher faces a difficult task of creating the most favorable, comfortable conditions for the comprehensive development of the student, creating a situation of success that will positively motivate and stimulate creative activity.

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